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XALQARO JURNAL**

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SIYOSAT VA JAMIYAT FALSAFASI

Hakimov Nazar Hakimovich

Liberalizm mafkurasi: genezisi, shakllanish omillari.....9-19

Shadiyev Bexzod Mirsalimovich

O‘zbekistondagi nodavlat notijorat tashkilotlar faoliyatini takomillashtirishning nazariy asoslari.....20-25

Alimatova Nargis Abduxalilovna

Raqobat mazmunining tarixiy evolyutsiyasi.....26-32

TA’LIM VA FAN FALSAFASI

Xidirov Mustafo Toyirqulovich

Abu Nasr Forobiy va Abu Ali ibn Sinoning bilish va faoliyat uyg‘unligiga oid tabiiy-ilmiy qarashlari.....33-40

Danilova V.S., Kojevnikov N.N.

Yevroosiyo madaniy kommunikatsiyalari va markazi: ontologik va metafizik jihatlari.....41-54

TARIX FALSAFASI VA FALSAFA TARIXI

Islamov Kamol Tashkulovich

Yevropa Uyg‘onish davri mutafakkirlari qarashlarida ijtimoiy-falsafiy fikrlar rivoji.....55-62

Burkhonov Sherzodbek Muxammadbobir ugli

Martin Xaydegger ta’limotidagi “Dasein” tushunchasi talqini.....63-68

Madalimov Timur Abduvaliyevich

Qadimgi Hindistonda Astika maktabining konseptual tahlili.....69-76

DUNYO MADANIYATI VA DINIY AN’ANALAR

Sagikizi Ayajan, Kakimjanova, Margarita Kabdulaevna, Qulibek Bagdatkali Abdimanapovich

Qozog‘iston jamiyatidagi ong transformatsiya sharoitlarida diniy qadriyatlar.....77-89

Saidzoda Daler Muxibullo

Zamonaviy jamiyat rivojlanishi sharoitlarida diniy-siyosiy ekstremizm tushunchasi tadqiqi.....90-98

Karimova Sadokat Tahirovna

Millatlararo totuvlikni ta’minlashda milliy o‘zlik va g‘urur tuyg‘ularining o‘rni.....99-109

ФИЛОСОФИЯ ПОЛИТИКИ И ОБЩЕСТВА

Хакимов Назар Хакимович

Идеология либерализма: генезис, факторы формирования.....9-19

Шадиев Бехзод Мирсалимович

Теоретические основы оптимизации деятельности неправительственных организаций в Узбекистане.....20-25

Алиматова Наргис Абдухалиловна

Историческая эволюция понятия соревнований.....26-32

ФИЛОСОФИЯ ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ И НАУКИ

Хидиров Мустафо Тойиркулович

Естественно-научные воззрения Абу Наср Фараби и Абу Али ибн Сина о гармонии познания и деятельности.....33-40

Данилова В.С., Кожевников Н.Н.

Центры и коммуникации культуры евразии: онтологические и метафизические аспекты.....41-54

ФИЛОСОФИЯ ИСТОРИИ И ИСТОРИЯ ФИЛОСОФИИ

Исламов Камол Ташкулович

Развитие социально-философских мыслей в мнениях мыслителей эпохи Возрождения Европы.....55-62

Бурханов Шерзодбека Мухаммадбобир угли

Интерпретация понятия «Dasein» у Мартина Хайдеггера.....63-68

Мадалимов Тимур Абдувалиевич

Концептуальный анализ школы Астика в древней Индии.....69-76

МИРОВАЯ КУЛЬТУРА И РЕЛИГИОЗНЫЕ ТРАДИЦИИ

Сагикызы Аяжан, Какимжанова Маргарита Кабдулаевна, Кулыбек Багдаткали Абдиманатович

Религиозные ценности в условиях трансформации сознания в Казахском обществе.....77-89

Саидзода Далер Мухибулло

Исследование понятия религиозно-политического экстремизма в контексте развития современного общества.....90-98

Каримова Садокат Тахировна

Роль чувств национальной идентичности и гордости в улучшении межнациональной гармонии.....99-109

PHILOSOPHY OF POLITICS AND SOCIETY

Hakimov Nazar Hakimovich

Ideology of liberalism: genesis, formation factors.....9-19

Shadiyev Behzod Mirsalimovich

Theoretical bases of the optimisation of the activities of non-governmental organizations in Uzbekistan.....20-25

Alimatova Nargis Abduxalilovna

Historical evolution of content of competition.....26-32

PHILOSOPHY OF EDUCATION AND SCIENCE

Khidirov Mustafo Toyirkulovich

The natural-scientific views of Abu Nasr Farabi and Abu Ali Ibn Sina on the harmony of cognition and activity.....33-40

Danilova V.S., Kojevnikov N.N.

Centers and communications of eurasian culture: ontological and metaphysical aspects.....41-54

PHILOSOPHY OF HISTORY AND HISTORY OF PHILOSOPHY

Islamov Kamol Tashkulovich

Development of social and philosophical thoughts in the opinions of the Renaissance Thinkers.....55-62

Burkhonov Sherzodbek Muxammadbobir o'g'li

Interpretation of the concept of "Dasein" in Martin Heidegger.....63-68

Madalimov Timur Abduvaliyevich

A conceptual analyse of the astika schools in ancient India.....69-76

WORLD CULTURE AND RELIGIOUS TRADITIONS

Sagikizi Ayajan, Kakimjanova, Margarita Kabdulayevna, Qulibek Bagdatkali Abdimanapovich

Religious values in the conditions of transformation of consciousness in the Kazakhstan society.....77-89

Saidzoda Daler Muxibullo

Study of the concept of religious-political extremism in the context of the development of modern society.....90-98

Karimova Sadokat Tahirovna

Role of national identity, pride the emotions in improving interethnic harmony.....99-109

Khidirov Mustafu Toyirkulovich

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THE NATURAL-SCIENTIFIC VIEWS OF ABU NASR FARABI AND ABU ALI IBN SINA ON THE HARMONY OF COGNITION AND ACTIVITY

Annotation. The scientific innovations formed on the basis of the views of the representatives of the Eastern philosophy of the Middle Ages took place due to internal and external reasons, due to favorable conditions of internal and external factors of the development of science. In this situation, the views of Abu Nasr Farabi and Abu Ali ibn Sina aimed at knowing the world served as a source of holistic knowledge. For science, which is considered a form of activity and a phenomenon, reflects the worldview of the period in which it exists, the influence of technical and production spheres in society.

Key words: knowledge, cognition, activity, philosophy, religion, society, culture, existence, Abu Nasr Farabi, Abu Ali ibn Sina, Greek philosophy.

ЕСТЕСТВЕННО-НАУЧНЫЕ ВОЗЗРЕНИЯ АБУ НАСР ФАРАБИ И АБУ АЛИ ИБН СИНА О ГАРМОНИИ ПОЗНАНИЯ И ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ

Аннотация. Научные новации, сформировавшиеся на основе взглядов представителей восточной философии средневековья, происходили благодаря внутренним и внешним причинам, благодаря благоприятным условиям внутренних и внешних факторов развития науки. В этой ситуации источником целостного знания послужили взгляды Абу Насра Фараби и Абу Али ибн Сины, направленные на познание мира. Ибо наука, которую считают формой деятельности и явлением, отражает мировоззрение того периода, в котором она существует, влияние технической и производственной сфер в обществе.

Ключевые слова: знание, познание, деятельность, философия, религия, общество, культура, существование, Абу Наср Фараби, Абу Али ибн Сина, греческая философия.

ABU NASR FOROBIY VA ABU ALI IBN SINONING BILISH VA FAOLIYAT UYG'UNLIGIGA OID TABIIY-ILMIY QARASHLARI

Annotatsiya. O'rta asrlar Sharq falsafasi vakillari qarashlari asosida shakllangan ilmiy yangiliklar ilm-fan rivojlanishining internal va eksternal sabablar, ichki va tashqi omillaridagi qulay shart-sharoitlar tufayli sodir bo'ldi. Shunday sharoitda Abu Nasr Forobiy va Abu Ali ibn Sinoning olamni bilishga qaratilgan qarashlari yaxlit bilimlar manbai sifatida xizmat qildi. Chunki faoliyat shakli va hodisasi hisoblangan ilm-fan o'zi mavjud bo'lgan davr dunyoqarashini, jamiyatdagi texnik va ishlab chiqarish sohalarining ham ta'siri kabilarni ham o'zida aks ettiradi.

Kalit so'zlar: bilim, bilish, faoliyat, falsafa, din, jamiyat, madaniyat, borliq, Abu Nasr Forobiy, Abu Ali ibn Sino, yunon falsafasi.

INTRODUCTION

In looking at the science as a cultural phenomenon we must note that, first, it contains the amalgamation of the knowledge base about the nature and natural phenomena. Secondly, it is a special sphere of activity in the life of the society. For this reason, science, which is a form of cognition, is considered universal and general phenomenon on the basis of general scientific research methods and it is considered as an evolutionary and multi-layered phenomenon. In this sense, although the evolution of epistemological views and their manifestation in activity in Eastern philosophy has its roots in ancient Greek philosophy, it reached a higher level based on the development of science under the influence of medieval Islamic culture. 'stretched. Because science, considered as a form of activity and a phenomenon, reflects the worldview of the period in which it exists, the influence of technical and production sectors in society, etc.

RESEARCH METHODS

The natural-scientific views of Abu Nasr Farabi and Abu Ali ibn Sina on the harmony of knowledge and activity were studied based on the review of their works and historical sources. Mechanisms of the development of natural and scientific knowledge in the Middle Ages were systematically analyzed using methods such as interrelatedness, objectivity, historicity, abstraction, principles of systematicity, analysis and synthesis.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

The knowledge formed in the stages of the development of philosophical thinking exists as a whole system from the VII-VIII centuries, and it combines the knowledge of social reality from the past and the present. They have mastered the historical-methodological principle consisting of a historical-logical approach in approaching their activities. That is why it is necessary to rely on the researches that have been researched about a research subject. At the same time, science cannot be affected by other spiritual spheres of society; it cannot stay away from

changes in finance, production, technical revolutions, and social structure of society, politics, education system and worldview.

It is known that the main factor of historical development is communication between different cultures and peoples, and if we look at history, there have always been various communication and mutual relations between peoples. The development and decline of science is determined not by geographical and climatic conditions, religious and racial origins of its representatives, but by the position of that nation or culture in this dialogue.

Ancient Greek mathematics was also influenced by the ancient East, but this did not destroy the independence of ancient Greece in terms of culture. [Жмудь. Л.Я., 1994: с. 164-177] The reason for the rise of Islamic culture in the Middle Ages was the fact that the Arabs occupied an important place in world communication, they occupied the blood vessels of world communication and connected the world with each other. Through trade caravans and sea trade routes under the control of the Arabs, not only spices, fabrics, various medicinal plants and aromatic perfumes were transported, but also geographical information, astronomical knowledge, works of art, samples of folk handicrafts, folk oral creativity and literature samples were also held. Large-scale trading activities served as a rich source for mathematical problems, long voyages stimulated the development of geographical and astronomical knowledge, and the development of handicrafts led to the development of the art of experimentation. Arab merchants prepared caravans and ships for travel, rich textile centers were located in the cities, wonderful weapons were produced, and gold and silver ornaments were made.

The presence of wide-ranging and specialized knowledge classified as medieval scientific knowledge by Al-Farabi testifies to the expansion of the field of cognitive activity in the middle ages of the Islamic era. The classification of sciences served as a road map among medieval scientific knowledge, which was wide-ranging and of a diverse nature, for choosing the right direction in the organization of the educational process, in the study of various sciences and knowledge. acted as a support in solving issues.

By getting acquainted with the classification of sciences and following the logic of their organization, it is possible to understand the basis of the science of the Muslim Middle Ages, its initial foundations, because in the formation of knowledge, instead of some forms of science, other forms of science are used. came The movement of thinking from simple to complex was reflected in the classification of sciences, in which certain principles of knowledge formation - through this understanding of the natural world, man, society and God - were observed. This process began with the development of sciences such as mathematics and logic, which prepared the human mind for thinking, and moreover, for the understanding of the natural world dominated by natural sciences such as medicine and chemistry. moved.

For historians of science, it is not an easy task to reconstruct such a complex cultural phenomenon as the science of the Islamic Middle Ages in a

methodologically correct way. The most important thing here is to single out the "joints" that unite the science, described in different ways in different scientific fields. These are the level of scientific conclusions reached in a certain field of science, the practical-experimental base in it, and the specific characteristics of each field of science. But it is they that allow the scientific phenomenon of a certain period to be whole and complete, and the same can be said about the science of the Islamic Middle Ages.

Islamic science in the Middle Ages preserved the models of closed theoretical science and empirical factual science that had already been formed in classical antiquity. In our opinion, in the philosophy of Eastern Peripateticism, in particular, in the views of al-Farabi, the tendency formed mainly in the philosophy of Plato - the model of theoretical science was of primary importance. In addition, we do not deny Farabi's contribution to the sciences of mathematics and astronomy, and according to the scientist, it was these sciences that made it possible to develop and master the axiomatic-deductive means of forming knowledge and proving it.

The thesis about the utilitarian-practical importance of Islamic medieval science cannot be a basis for denying its theoretical character, but the above-mentioned factual, descriptive and empirical scientific knowledge, which Islamic medieval science is really close to practice. It serves to confirm the thesis that it reflects the model. In particular, this aspect can be observed in the legacy of Farabi, and today scientists are writing in their research about the importance of Farabi's contribution to the field of applied mathematics and mechanics. However, in our opinion, the most characteristic science for him was theoretical science. For example, comparing Galen's research method with Aristotle's research method, Farabi writes the following: "Each of these methods originates from truly universal and individual views, which are seen as reliable knowledge. The concept of "reliable knowledge" means relatively real and reliable knowledge, and we can get information about this in the book "Proof". Theoretical science first aims to study what a thing is, what its definition refers to, and its materiality. The condition of reliable truth is to know the existence and the reasons for the existence of things [Аль-Фараби, 1975: с. 42-43].

It should be recognized that, despite the fact that in the Middle Ages, scientific research was the activity of individual individuals who made up a small part of society, it was able to rise to the level of development of theoretical constructions. Based on the criteria of scientific rationality accepted in that historical situation, their fundamental, philosophical levels were not questioned. As an example, the following opinion of Farabi can be given: "... the influence of this art can be felt only when continuous research is carried out. Therefore, reading it should come only after reading philosophy. A person who intends to study this science should increase his knowledge about various fields of philosophy, because philosophy is a source of absolute wisdom, and mastering it will allow a person to understand the real state of things and reach the essence of this art [Аль-Фараби, 1975: с. 190].

Although such a situation is mainly observed in natural sciences and not observed in mathematical sciences, in science both knowledge in the form of ordinary facts gathered on the basis of simple language and observation, and observations valid at the level of common sense are considered. Therefore, in the science of the Islamic Middle Ages, different layers of scientific knowledge can be observed, and they consist of many layers and many periods of scientific development. The same point can be made about the science of earlier periods in which the knowledge that man acquires consists mainly of scientific mythology, or where scientific mythology predominates, but which also has targets that serve as a basis for later discoveries.

It was the developed intellectual constructions in this logic that made it possible to consolidate these different layers in the science of the Middle Ages of Islam, bring them into a unified form, and talk about science as a system of integrated knowledge. Eastern peripatetics had priority in solving ontological issues, as well as in developing deductive methods of knowledge generation. Since the Eastern Peripatetics believed that to know the things in the universe was to know their cause, they believed that the universe depended on the causal cause, Existence Wajib, or necessary existence that caused everything to come into existence.

Based on the socio-political and ideological situation of his time, the thinker tried to preserve the scientific rationalist thinking and harmonize scientific concepts with religious beliefs. It is necessary to say that in the philosophy of Farabi, the mind is considered as a product created by Allah, which means that Allah created the mind as a result of strict necessity [Юлдашев.Ф.А., 2018: 20 б.].

Based on these views, it can be said that the universe can be explained through the chain of cause and effect, and the order of existence is exactly that. As Ibn Sina wrote, "... all things do not have to have the same quality in order for the importance of all things to be at the same level, in the same position, in relation to the wajib, it simply manifests itself through the order of succession between things..." [Ибн Сина 1980: с. 106] This sequence is based on the Platonic philosophy of the origin of all forms of existence through emanation from the Primordial Being.

A clear example of the ontological view of the world in the philosophy of Islamic peripatetics is the philosophy of Abu Nasr al Farabi, who is considered one of the bright representatives of the concept of emanation. Among the philosophers of the medieval Islamic world, U.M. Watt considers Al Farabi "one of the world's greatest philosophers" and argues that his views are relevant [Уотт У.М., 2008: с. 75].

Strengths, abilities and learned actions that help a person to realize his goals are human good. The forces, abilities and learned voluntary actions that prevent a person from realizing the goals he has set for him are human vices. [Хайруллаев М.М., 1963: б. 45].

The solution of the increasingly important methodological issue of the eastern-peripatetic rationality of the world structure, the issue of views on the

orderly universe presented in the sacred source, was carried out through the principles close to neoplatonism, or the concept of emanation. Al-Farabi defines the Neoplatonic concept of existence as the First Cause bringing other things into existence, because its existence is such that "all forms of existence, whether perfect or imperfect, proceed from it; also, its characteristic is such that all forms of existence arise from it according to their level and have their own form of existence; therefore, imperfect things gradually acquire more imperfect forms of existence, and this process descends to the simplest levels of existence, to the level of non-existence. [Аль-Фараби, 1972: с. 228-229].

According to Ibn Sina, who is considered the most prominent representative of the school of Peripatetics in the Islamic Middle Ages, all the philosophical views of al-Farabi are reflected in his general conclusion, i.e., his observations on determining the causes of all existing things. From the biographical works on Ibn Sina, it is possible to know how much al-Farabi influenced his views on "Metaphysics". [Ибн Сина, 1980: Т. 1; с. 58]. That is why the ontological problem, its foundation, disclosure and solution by Ibn Sina is carried out within the framework of Farabiism, which shows the potential of Aristotelianism in general.

As for things that come before and after in nature, everything that manifests itself is finite and has a beginning and an end. Causation is related to the occurrence of such an occurrence that, according to Ibn Sina, it cannot be infinite and has a finite, fixed cause. Ibn Sina justifies this in the following way: "The actual causes of something can be the cause in one case, and the cause of the cause in the other case; according to their nature, they have the property of coming before and coming after, so they do not have the property of infinity [Ибн Сина, 1980: Т. 1; с. 58].

Wherever there is such an order, there is some kind of first cause. If causes were infinite, there would be no uncaused cause among them, or at least one uncaused cause would be required. If even an uncaused particle had a cause, it would be considered a limited causality, not an infinite one.

If nothing existed without a cause, they would all be effects, and they would all exist in reality, for if something is to be one of an infinite number of things, then it is a collection of things. It cannot be a consequence because it consists of real existing consequences. But if we take into account that this collection is an effect, their cause must be outside themselves. If this cause is an effect, it should be included in this collection; but we agreed that it is outside this set, so it cannot be a consequence, so it is limited. [Ибн Сина, 1980, с. 128].

Therefore, looking at the world from the point of view of causal relations, Ibn Sina concludes about the final cause of this world and says that it should be understood as the active, active cause and starting point of the world.

Ibn Sina does not deny the power of the first cause. He justifies this with a rationalist, rational tool, based on logical arguments. For example, in the chapter of Metaphysics known as "Explanation of the Status of the Power of Necessary Essence," Shaykh ur-Rais writes: "It may be said that everything that is in His will

exists, and that everything that is not in His will does not come from things that do not originate from Him." And that which was in his power, though unfit for his power, would have been; and that which is not in his power could not exist even if he willed it. In this sense, they say that there is no power more powerful than knowledge, because its power is measured by its ability to know things, knowing the essence of things and being powerful are not two different qualities [Ибн Сина, 1980, с. 152].

It is unacceptable to blame the medieval philosopher for not being able to rise to the level of dialectical understanding of cause and effect, characteristic of the later periods of the development of philosophy. Essentially, the entire Arab-Muslim philosophy. His emphasis on question and practice led philosophers such as Ibn Sina to achieve great achievements in the fields of inference and practice, led to a methodological understanding of the role and importance of the principle of doubt, and finally in the field of general concepts, that is, dialectic. It has prepared the ground for the beginning of the search for truth in the field of logic.

CONCLUSION

Being aware of the legacy of their great ancestors gives the young generation spiritual strength and forms civic responsibility for the fate of their homeland. It requires understanding the process of today's socio-political, spiritual and cultural changes. In particular, the natural-scientific views of Abu Nasr Farabi and Abu Ali ibn Sina on the harmony of knowledge and activity serve to understand the dialectics of history and today. It is impossible to imagine the development of science in the Middle Ages without the ideas and philosophical views of Plato and Aristotle. Because the development of philosophical thinking is perfected as a result of transience and goes towards the holistic understanding of the world. We can analyze on the basis of historical knowledge that the views of representatives of Greek philosophy have changed from a historical-logical approach to a historical-methodological approach. In this case, the social development of knowledge is closely related to the society in addition to the individual thinking of a person, and this means succession. On the other hand, in the conditions of the diversity of opinions, there are also scientists who doubt the objective development of science in the Middle Ages and emphasize that there are insufficient scientific foundations. The period of Eastern renaissance created a favorable environment for the study of the natural world due to various social and political influences and prohibitions, and thereby encouraging free research activities.

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